

Review Article

Vitamin C and human diseases: An overview

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**Mediterranean Journal of
Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical
Sciences**

Article information

Received
24-10-2021

Revised
07-11-2021

Accepted
11-12-2021

Published
31-12-2021

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<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0870-9271>**Abstract**

Vitamin C is associated with history of the cause of the ancient hemorrhagic disease scurvy. Vitamin C is an essential nutrient with important antioxidant properties. It is required by the body for normal physiological function. The body cannot synthesize vitamin C, it is present in nature through foods and other natural sources and it exists as a nutritional food supplement. The antioxidant activity of vitamin C protects the body from free radical damage. Vitamin C is essential for the development and maintenance of connective tissues. It is used as therapeutic agent in many diseases and disorders. Vitamin C plays an important role in several metabolic functions, as the conversion of the amino acid, tryptophan, to the neurotransmitter, serotonin, and the conversion of cholesterol to bile acids. Vitamin C supplementation resulted in a significant increase in vitamin C levels in populations; its high intake is associated with positive effects on cardiovascular risk factors. Vitamin C protects the immune system, reduces the severity of allergic reactions and helps to fight infections. It has an important role in bone formation, wound healing and the maintenance of healthy gums. There is profound beneficial effect of vitamin C in respect to human diseases as cancer, atherosclerosis, diabetes, neurodegenerative disease and many metal toxicities. Several vitamin C analogs have been produced as anticancer and antioxidant activity. Vitamin C is useful if it is used as adjuvant therapy for several chronic diseases. Thus, this review summarizes the importance of vitamin C in the body's physiology and biochemistry, in addition, the different mechanisms that vitamin C is implicated to treat different acute and chronic diseases. Future exploration should pay attention to chronic disease management by vitamin C.

DOI (not yet)**Keywords:** Ascorbic acid, chronic disease, disease, metabolic disorders, prevention, vitamin C

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HOW TO CITE THIS: Aburawi SM (2021) Vitamin C and human diseases: An overview. *Mediterr J Pharm Pharm Sci* 1(4): 25-36. Doi: (not yet)

Introduction

Vitamin C (ascorbic acid) is a vital nutrient for health and is an essential vitamin required by human bodies for normal physiological function [1, 2]. It is an antioxidant that protects the body from free radical damage [3] and deleterious effects of pollutants and toxins. Vitamin C is an essential nutrient involved in many biological and biochemical processes as an antioxidant; it prevents the development of various diseases due to oxidative damage [4]. Human bodies are unable to synthesize vitamin C due to the absence of gluconolactone oxidase enzyme, which is required for the formation of vitamin C from glucose and galactose [3]. Therefore, they must obtain it from

dietary sources [5]. Vitamin C has widely been found in citrus fruits, strawberries, tomatoes, broccoli, Brussels sprouts, green peppers, red peppers, turnips, and many other leafy vegetables [6]. It plays a central role in the antioxidant defense system and exists in two major forms. The charged form, ascorbate, is taken up into cells via sodium-dependent facilitated transport. The uncharged form, dehydroascorbate, enters cells via glucose transporter, then converted back to ascorbate within these cells [7]. Its absorption in the buccal cavity is by passive diffusion and in the gastrointestinal tract absorption is by active sodium-dependent vitamin C transporters (SVCT) [8, 9]. Bioavailability of vitamin C is reduced in stress, alcohol intake, smoking, fever, viral illnesses, antibiotics,

and pain killers use; also observed when exposure to petroleum products or carbon monoxide and heavy metals toxicity. Low vitamin C levels in the body could be due to increased utilization and/or decreased absorption from the gut [3]. Vitamin C metabolites are primarily eliminated through urine [6]. The concentration in the body represents a very sensitive index of oxidative stress [10].

Antioxidant micronutrients and antioxidant enzymes are considered the body's defense systems against free radicals and reactive molecules. The production of highly reactive oxygen metabolites is normal in cellular metabolism. The formation of the highly reactive oxygen metabolites is needed in the body's natural immune system, mitochondrial respiratory chain, arachidonic acid metabolism, ovulation and fertilization [11]. The excessive production of free-radical species is continuous in the human body which indicates pathological condition [11]. The body requires vitamin C, for normal physiological functions. It helps in the synthesis and metabolism of tyrosine, folic acid and tryptophan, hydroxylation of glycine, proline, lysine carnitine and catecholamine [3]. Vitamin C is present with a high concentration in the adrenal gland, where it is required both in catecholamine biosynthesis and in adrenal steroidogenesis [12]. It facilitates the conversion of cholesterol into bile acids and hence lowers blood cholesterol levels [3]. It increases the absorption of iron in GIT by reducing ferric to ferrous state [3]. It was observed that vitamin C in vitro acts as an antioxidant by preventing iron-induced lipid peroxidation [13]. It was reported that orally supplemented vitamin C in guinea pigs with iron overload acts as an antioxidant by suppressing lipid oxidation [14]. In healthy humans, vitamin C at 40 - 80 μM of plasma concentration exerts antioxidant activity, in which vitamin C donates an electron to free radicals and reduces the potentially damaging effects [15]. At the same time, vitamin C is oxidized into unreactive ascorbate radical, which is converted back to vitamin C through NADH/NADPH-dependent reductases [15]. As an antioxidant, vitamin C repairs the tocopheroxyl radical of vitamin E, permitting vitamin E to function again as an antioxidant [16]. Vitamin C protects DNA, amino acid residues and lipids from oxidation induced by free radicals and maintains their integrity [17], preventing them from harmful mutations [2]. Decreased blood levels of vitamin C are associated with diabetes mellitus [18], acute pancreatitis [19], asthma [20] or an unstable coronary syndrome [21]. Deficiency of vitamin C is observed with anemia, infections, bleeding gums, scurvy, poor wound healing, capillary hemorrhage, muscle degeneration, atherosclerotic plaques and neurotic disturbances. Large doses of vitamin C are required to correct the deficiency, and unlike fat-soluble vitamins, toxicity is rare [3]. Vitamin C intake for reduction of chronic disease risks

such as cancer and cardiovascular diseases should be higher than the recommended dietary allowances (RDA) [22].

Vitamin C and survey

Low levels of vitamin C in the body can lead to scurvy [1]. People needed just 10 mg of vitamin C per day to avoid scurvy [23].

Vitamin C and common cold

Vitamin C has a known health beneficial effect in prevention and relief of common cold [24]. In the common cold, the immunity is attenuated. Vitamin C boosts immunity during rhinitis; it stimulates the immune system by enhancing T-cell proliferation in response to infection. These cells are capable of lysing infected targets by producing large quantities of cytokines and by helping B cells to synthesize immunoglobulins to control inflammatory reactions. Also, vitamin C blocks pathways that lead to apoptosis of T-cells and stimulate or maintain T-cell proliferation to attack the infection [3]. The antioxidant properties of vitamin C are useful during the common cold. In an infection, phagocytic leukocytes activation produces oxidizing compounds that are released from the cells. Vitamin C reacts with these oxidants and may decrease the inflammatory effects that they produce [25]. Several clinical trials of vitamin C, with different doses, showed that it does not have a significant prophylactic effect, but reduces the severity and duration of symptoms of cold during the period of infection [26].

Vitamin C and cardiovascular diseases

Diet rich in fruits and vegetables is highly protective against atherosclerosis and coronary heart disease [27]. Frequent intake of fruit and vegetables, that are rich in vitamin C, increases the activity of the fibrinolytic system by lowering plasminogen activator inhibitor activity [28]. Increased fibrinogen concentrations increase the risk of acute or chronic infection and cardiovascular disease. Administration of vitamin C in a dose of 2 gm per day, increases fibrinolytic activity and decreases the platelet adhesive index and serum cholesterol [29]. Vitamin C is important for the production of collagen, which plays a role in heart health by maintaining blood vessel walls [23]. Daily administration of vitamin C is useful to control blood pressure in hypertensive patients [30]. The higher serum levels of vitamin C significantly lower systolic and diastolic blood pressure among middle-aged or elderly populations [31, 32]. The powerful antioxidant effect of

vitamin C reverses endothelial dysfunction due to increased oxidative stress, and prevents hyperoxic vasoconstriction [33]; it also improves lipid-induced impairment of endothelium-dependent vasodilation [34]. Vitamin C may improve nitric oxide production, [1] that relaxes and widens blood vessels [35]. Total cholesterol, low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL) and high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL) are considered major risk factors for cardiovascular disease [36]. Oxidation of lipoproteins may promote atherosclerosis [37]. The oxidized LDL has an atherogenic potential due to lipid peroxidation [38]. Vitamin C protects against neutrophil-mediated LDL oxidation; this may be due to the scavenging of extracellular oxidants, also prevents pro-oxidant effects of urate in LDL oxidation [39]. Vitamin C may protect from atherosclerosis by strengthening the artery walls through its participation in the synthesis of collagen and preventing the undesirable adhesion of white blood cells to damaged arteries [40]. A clinical study concludes that co-administration of vitamin C with the regular use of anti-hypertensive drugs helped in decreasing systolic and diastolic blood pressure of hypertensive patients compared to patients with antihypertensive therapy only. Further, the use dose of vitamin C (500 mg/day) induced a significant increase in vitamin C plasma concentrations accompanied by a reduction in LDL, TC, TG and an increase in the beneficial HDL [41].

Vitamin C and neuropsychiatric disorders

Oxidative stress may play a role in neurodegenerative diseases, such as Alzheimer's disease that causes dementia and is associated with aging [42]; also Schizophrenia, is associated with morbidity and economic burden [3]. Several studies investigated the role of increased free radical generation in the pathogenesis of schizophrenia. In schizophrenics, it was detected that there are changes in the optimum activities of antioxidant enzymes [43, 44] and related parameters of lipid peroxidation [45, 46] in blood. The brain contains a large amount of unsaturated fatty acids, and catecholamine, which are considered the target molecules for lipid peroxidation [47, 48]. A significant rise in oxidative stress and decreased antioxidant status was observed in the chronic stage of schizophrenia as compared to those in acute condition [3]. A decrease in the levels of vitamin C was found in schizophrenics compared to normal controls. Vitamin C supplement produces a reduction in a brief psychiatric rating scale (BPRS) and positive and negative syndrome scale score [49]. Vitamin C, an antioxidant

vitamin, plays an important role in protecting free radical-induced damage in the brain [3]. The increase in dehydrovitamin C and fall in reduced vitamin C at the same time suggests scavenging action of vitamin C and its utilization with increased oxidative stress as indicated by high blood malondialdehyde levels [50]. A clinical study found that co-administration of vitamin C with antidepressants therapy decreased significantly the total Hamilton Depression Rating Scale (HDRS) scores. Vitamin C was therapeutically benefited with an antidepressant in the treatment of depression and predicts a good response; it was well tolerated and effective in improving depressive symptoms [51].

Vitamin C and cancer

In the human body, reactive oxygen species (ROS) are generated during physiological and pathological processes [52] but high levels of ROS contribute to carcinogenesis [53]. ROS attacks cellular DNA causing damage and genomic instability leading to mutations that incorporate the development of neoplastic characteristics [54]. Antioxidant activity of vitamin C may help reduce inflammation and decrease the risk of developing various conditions of cancers [1]. It was shown that vitamin C may have a role in cancer prevention [4]. In a clinical study of elderly patients with acute myeloid leukemia, vitamin C with anticancer agents had a better rate of complete remission and overall survival without any substantial toxicity as compared to the anticancer agents alone [55].

A high dose of vitamin C is important for exerting the anticancer effect [2]. Evidence that vitamin C alone may not be effective enough in the treatment of most active cancers, but it improves the quality of life and extends longevity in cancer patients. Therefore, vitamin C should be given as a supplement in cancer therapy [6]. High-dose of vitamin C administration improved the survival of patients with terminal cancer [56, 57]. In vitro study showed that a high concentration of vitamin C is toxic to cancer cells [58]. Intravenous administration of vitamin C may act as a pro-drug for the formation of hydrogen peroxide, causing the death of cancer cells without affecting the normal cells [59]. Vitamin C produces apoptosis of cancer cells by acting as pro-oxidant and increasing intracellular reactive oxygen species levels [60]. Mechanisms involved of vitamin C in the treatment and prevention of cancer are: enhancing the immune system; stimulating the formation of collagen; preventing metastasis by inhibiting enzymes; preventing viruses that can cause cancer; correction of vitamin C deficiency,

which is often associated with cancer patients [61]. Experimental and clinical studies observed that high vitamin C concentration leads to tumor shrinkage [59, 62]. Intravenous vitamin C administration in cancer therapy selectively kills tumor cells in vitro. This tumor-killing phenomenon is because of the pro-oxidant property of vitamin C, due to the production of hydrogen peroxide [59]. Vitamin C generates H_2O_2 in cancer cells [63] through metals reduction such as copper and iron reaction [64], leading to selective cytotoxicity to cancer cells [63]. Vitamin C, as an antioxidant, enhances the effectiveness of chemotherapy and reduces its toxicity, and increases survival rate [61, 65]. Administration of vitamin C decreases the formation of nitrosamines, which is associated with gastric cancer [66]. Lipophilic derivative of vitamin C as Ascorbyl stearate can cross the cell membranes and blood-brain barrier; it inhibits cell proliferation by interfering with cell cycle and induces apoptosis by modulation of insulin-like growth factor 1-receptor expression in T98G and pancreatic cancer cells [67]. Vitamin C hinders cancer progression by targeting different susceptible nodes such as Hypoxia-inducible factor (HIF), Glucose transporter 1 (GLUT1), and mutated genes of ten-eleven translocation (TET) enzymes. It is known that Hypoxia-inducible factor 1 (HIF-1) activates the transcription of genes that are involved in crucial aspects of cancer biology, including cell survival, glucose metabolism, and invasion [68]. Hypoxia-inducible factor controls the expression of genes linked to angiogenesis, anti-apoptotic activity, stem cell renewal, metastasis, and therapeutic resistance of cancer cells [2]. Higher doses of vitamin C reduce DNA damage and mutations through degradation of HIF-1 α levels [69]. Cancer cells must increase glucose uptake, to ensure the flux of sugar into metabolic pathways; therefore, GLUT1 is an important target in cancer treatment [22]. Targeting GLUT1 activity is a promising strategy for the development of drugs aimed at treating neoplastic growth [70]. Mutated genes (TET) proteins are associated with the activation of cancer stem cells by altering the metabolic and epigenetic profiles of cells [2]. The activity of TETs is an important factor in numerous developmental stages in physiological function, and disruption can lead to failure of cell type-specific functions [71]. Disruption of the ten-eleven translocation (TET) is an early event in the onset of disease. It is now known that all three TET genes are mutated and show reduced expression, and the proteins have impaired activity in a wide range of different cancer types [71]. DNA methylation abnormalities are often observed in

diseases. The ten-eleven translocation (TET) enzymes oxidize 5-methylcytosines (5 mCs) and promote locus-specific reversal of DNA methylation [71].

Vitamin C and diabetes mellitus

Diabetes mellitus is associated with increased production of reactive oxygen species and a reduction in antioxidant defenses [7, 72]. Oxidative stress is a common pathogenetic factor of diabetic nephropathy [7]. Tubular epithelial cells are dehydroascorbate dependent; a decrease in vitamin C levels in tubular epithelial cells through competition of glucose and dehydroascorbate for common transport mechanism in diabetes will deprive the cells of antioxidant, this may lead to reactive oxygen species accumulation [7]. Insulin increases the active cellular uptake of vitamin C, while hyperglycemia inhibits renal vitamin C reabsorption. Because dehydroascorbate and glucose compete for glucose transporters, hyperglycemia discharges vitamin C from tubular epithelial cells, resulting in decreased antioxidant capacity [7].

Vitamin C and fertility

Vitamin C is essential for the structural and functional integrity of androgen-dependent reproductive organs [3]; its concentration in seminal plasma is higher than plasma concentration [73], and the percentage of sperm with normal morphology correlated significantly with seminal vitamin C levels [3]. The deficiency of vitamin C may produce oxidative damage induced by reactive oxygen species (ROS); an increase in ROS was observed in the semen of infertile men [74]. In a human trial, a decrease in vitamin C levels was associated with an increase in seminal plasma lipid peroxidation [75]; it may also lead to abnormal sperm parameters [76]. Low concentration of vitamin C produced marked degenerative changes in the testes, epididymis, and vas deferens of scorbutic guinea pigs [77], also produced degeneration of the spermatogenic epithelium, steroidogenesis, and decline in plasma testosterone levels [78]. As an antioxidant, vitamin C improves sperm quality in a dose-dependent manner in men [79], increases progesterone levels in infertile women with luteal phase defect [80]. An animal experimental study showed that vitamin C improves antioxidant enzymes activity and reduces malondialdehyde (MDA) in testis [81]. It was reported that vitamin C supplementation leads to a significant reduction in ROS concentration [82], sperm membrane lipid peroxidation [83] and sperm DNA oxidation [82], and increased sperm quality [83]. Polycystic ovary

syndrome induced by formaldehyde produces a histological alteration in the ovary and uterus of female mice reproductive system; vitamin C administration has prophylaxis and treatment role against this damage induced by formaldehyde [84].

Vitamin C and atherosclerosis

Development of atherosclerosis may be due to lipid peroxidation and oxidative modification of LDL [85]; initiation of atherosclerosis can be due to adhesion of leukocytes to the endothelium. Vitamin C helps in the prevention of atherosclerosis by strengthening the artery walls through its participation in the synthesis of collagen, and by preventing the undesirable adhesion of white blood cells to damaged arteries [85]. In vivo studies showed that vitamin C inhibits leukocyte-endothelial cell interactions induced by cigarette smoke [86]. Vitamin C, as an antioxidant, scavenges free radicals and thus prevents the oxidation of LDL [39], even in passive smokers [87]. A deficiency of vitamin C leads to enhance the accumulation of cholesterol in the thoracic aorta along with pathomorphological changes in blood vessels [3], also leading to impaired cholesterol metabolism resulting in atheromatous changes in the vascular system [88]. High intake of vitamin C reduces the risk of stroke in half compared to those with the lowest intake [89]. A cohort study suggested that cardiovascular mortality was reduced in both sexes by vitamin C [90]. Vitamin C administration causes a significant reduction in LDL and a nonsignificant increase in HDL and protects against coronary artery disease [91].

Vitamin C and asthma & obstructive pulmonary disease

Vitamin C plays an essential role in defending against oxidant attack in the airways; its deficiency in asthmatics sputum may be a factor in the pathophysiology of asthma or a response to asthmatic airway inflammation [25].

Vitamin C and immunity

In humans, vitamin C has immune potentiating benefit [4], while in guinea pigs, increases serum levels of antibodies [92]. Vitamin C concentrations in the plasma and leukocytes rapidly decline during infections and stress [93]. Administration of vitamin C improves the human immune system such as antimicrobial and NK cell activities, lymphocyte proliferation. Vitamin C maintains the redox integrity of cells and protects them against ROS generated during the respiratory burst and in the

inflammatory response [93]. Vitamin C reverses the damage caused by free radicals at a cellular level, modulates immune cell functions through the regulation of redox-sensitive transcription factors, and affects the production of cytokines and prostaglandins [3]. Intravenous vitamin C treatment reduces pro-inflammatory cytokines IL-1 α , IL-2, IL-8, TNF- α [94]. Vitamin C inhibits the excessive activation of the immune system leading to prevent tissue damage; it supports antibacterial activity [95]. A study conclude that vitamin C showed a significant antibacterial effect on both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria and enhanced the effect of the Penicillin G [96].

Vitamin C and allergies

There is evidence that low vitamin C levels were common in people with allergies [1]. During an allergic reaction, the immune system triggers an inflammatory response that leads to symptoms such as swelling and hives. During this process, the body produces ROS, which leads to oxidative stress [1]. A high dose of vitamin C (IV) may help reduce allergy symptoms [1].

Vitamin C and tissue healing

Wound healing requires synthesis and accumulation of collagen and subsequent cross-linking of the fiber for new tensile strength to the damaged tissue [97, 98]. Vitamin C is important for the production of collagen, which binds together wounds, allowing them to heal [23]. Vitamin C is necessary for the normal healing process especially for post-operative patients; its administration is recommended to accelerate the healing process [99]. In clinical studies, evidence that wound healing in subjects not deficient in vitamin C significantly accelerated with vitamin C daily dose [99]. In cultured human keratinocytes, vitamin C acts as a modulator of proliferation and differentiation, directly affecting the keratinocyte or indirectly through effects on fibroblasts [100]. Vitamin C modulates the growth and maturation of chondrocytes and accelerates bone fracture healing [101].

Vitamin C and pain

Vitamin C has analgesic effect for neuropathic pain [102]. Antinociceptive action of vitamin C is through the activation of the dopamine pathway, as this effect was blocked by metoclopramide. Vitamin C may also modulate its analgesic effect through 5HT release [102] because this action was inhibited by ondansetron [103]. In addition, vitamin C may produce its antinociception by

interaction with ionotropic glutamate receptors; NMDA receptor is involved during neuropathic pain which is redox-regulated [104] for these reasons, arachidonic acid could possess a role in modulating nociceptive processes. In addition, vitamin C inhibits p38-dependent nociceptive signaling in spinal cord microglia and dorsal root ganglia neurons [105].

Vitamin C and pain pollution

Air pollution consists of various substances and chemicals that may produce a negative impact on people's health. Vitamin C with antioxidant effect may reduce symptoms of asthma and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease [1].

Vitamin C and cataract

Vitamin C is found in high concentrations in the lens, and is important for the prevention of cataracts in the older population [106]. It is believed that oxidative stress may be a factor in the conditions; therefore, vitamin C could be useful with its antioxidant activity [1].

Vitamin C and anemia

Vitamin C is known to enhance the availability and absorption of iron from non-heme iron sources [107]. It enhances the absorption of iron; healthcare professionals recommend taking vitamin C supplements with iron tablets to improve absorption in people with iron deficiency anemia [1]. Observations showed that vitamin C inhibits the expression of hepcidin [108]; hepcidin is the master regulator of systemic iron homeostasis, tightly influences erythrocyte production. High hepcidin levels block intestinal iron absorption and macrophage iron recycling, causing iron-restricted erythropoiesis and anemia [109]. Vitamin C is a novel modulator for the classical transferrin Fe²⁺ uptake pathway, acting through intracellular reductive mechanism [110].

Vitamin C and cigarette

Cigarette smokers are exposed to a large number of oxidants [111]. Vitamin C levels in the plasma of smokers were depleted by smoking compared to nonsmokers [112].

Cigarette smoking is associated with endothelial dysfunction with impaired endothelium-dependent flow-mediated dilation [113]. Vitamin C improves the endothelial function in chronic smokers and restores impaired coronary flow velocity reserve against oxidative stress in smokers [114].

Vitamin C and DNA

In the human body, reactive oxygen species (ROS) attacks cellular DNA and produce damage and genomic instability; this leads to mutations and the development of neoplastic disorders [54]. High vitamin C intake protects DNA, amino acid residues, and lipids from oxidation induced by free radicals and maintains their integrity [17], preventing them from harmful mutations [2]. The deficiency of vitamin C produces damage to DNA by causing single- and double-strand breaks and oxidative lesions [115].

Vitamin C pre-oxidant role

Vitamin C in micromolar concentrations has anti-oxidant activity, while in millimolar concentrations has pro-oxidant activity. The pro-oxidant activity is useful in inducing cytotoxicity to tumor cells [116]. In an experimental study, vitamin C in millimolar concentrations donates an electron to copper and iron metals, leading to the production of superoxide, hydrogen peroxide-like ROS [64]. Vitamin C reduces Fe³⁺/Cu²⁺ to ferrous (Fe²⁺)/cuprous (Cu⁺) ions and oxidizes itself into ascorbate free radical (Asc⁻). The reduced Fe²⁺/Cu⁺ ions react with oxygen to form ROS such as superoxide radicals, leading to the formation of hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂). Hydrogen peroxide is catalyzed by Fe²⁺/Cu⁺, yielding hydroxyl peroxide radical (HO·) [16, 117].

Vitamin C and toxicity

High consumption of vitamin C and its metabolites such as dehydrovitamin C, 2,3-diketogulonic acid, and oxalic acid is excreted via the kidney in humans; it may cause gastrointestinal disturbances or diarrhea [118]. Vitamin C in the presence of heavy metal results in the production of ROS as superoxide ion, hydrogen peroxide, and hydroxyl radical; this enhances lipid peroxidation, DNA damage, and altered calcium and sulfhydryl homeostasis [3]. Vitamin C metabolism will break down in tissues to dehydrovitamin C, then to diketogulonic acid, and then catabolized to oxalate, which is excreted in urine [119]. Documented cases that daily intake greater than 2 gm per day can induce oxalate crystal nephropathy [120]. The supersaturated oxalate in the tubules leads to deposits as crystals and develops stones that in turn damage the tubular epithelium [121]. Oxalate nephropathy induced by vitamin C can lead to chronic renal disease; this may need long-term dialysis or transplantation, and even death [122]. Cadmium is an extremely toxic metal commonly found in industrial workplaces, it causes lipid peroxidative changes in various tissues. Vitamin C intake has a protective role in the lung and brain of rats exposed to excessive cadmium [123]. Vitamin C restores the

hematological changes in mercury and cadmium exposed Wistar rats [124]. Vitamin C also has a protective function against concomitant exposure to heavy metals and radiation [125]. Experimental studies report the beneficial effect of vitamin C against heavy metal toxicity. Lead is the common environmental poison in which vitamin C has a protective role [126]. A study showed that lead-induced electrophysiological changes in rat colon; were inhibited by vitamin C administration [127]. Arsenic toxicity is essentially associated with lipid peroxidation and oxidative stress. Arsenic in drinking water may even cause chromosomal aberration leading to molecular disorders [128]. Arsenic exposure during gestation and lactation leads to increased lipid peroxidation in the rat brain, which was reversed by vitamin C administration [129]. Arsenic induced hepatotoxicity; vitamin C supplementation improves mitochondrial structure and function along with restriction of apoptosis due to caspase-3 inhibition in arsenic trioxide exposed rat liver [130].

Interaction and Vitamin C

Clinical study showed that the administration of vitamin C combined with antidepressant therapy reduced Hamilton depression rating scale compared to the antidepressant therapy effect without vitamin C administration. This indicates that vitamin C improves antidepressant therapy and reduces their side effects [51]. The same clinical study showed that agitation, anxiety (psychotic and somatic) and hypochondrias were improved by vitamin C administration. Symptoms of depression that improved with vitamin C administration are depressed mood, feeling of guilt, suicide, early insomnia, middle insomnia, late insomnia, weight loss [131]. Using Cup Cut Diffusion Method, Vitamin C showed a significant antibacterial effect on both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria and enhanced the effect of penicillin G [96]. In a study using the same technique, vitamin C produced an inhibitory effect on the growth of gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria. Vitamin C potentiated the effect of ciprofloxacin at low concentrations (10 mg/ml), while vitamin C at higher concentrations (20 and 40 mg/ml) antagonized the inhibitory effect of ciprofloxacin on gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria [132]. Using averted gut sac technique of albino rats, Vitamin C absorption was increased by time, either alone or in the presence of black tea extract. Black tea extract increased the absorption of vitamin C compared to the absorption of vitamin C alone [133]. A neurobehavioral study showed that vitamin C produced dose-dependent anxiolytic effects, using albino

rats. The combined treatment of vitamin C with Alprazolam did not potentiate the anxiolytic action, but it has additive effects [35, 134, 135]. Acute administration of vitamin C was accompanied by an increase in GABA levels in almost all brain areas studied, leading to anxiolytic action [134]. Flumazenil and Picrotoxin abolished the anxiolytic action of vitamin C in elevated plus-maze; this indicates that the action of vitamin C is mediated through the benzodiazepine/GABA_A receptor. Vitamin C levels in the brain were found to be regionally dependent: higher levels were found in the anterior regions, such as the cerebral cortex and mid-brain, with progressively lower levels in more-posterior regions, such as the brainstem and cerebellum. Alprazolam did not affect vitamin C levels in all brain areas studied [135]. Vitamin C causes a significant change in the pharmacological effects of some drugs, which may lead to unpredictable responses. Recently, vitamin C decreases extrapyramidal side effects caused by the antipsychotic haloperidol; it successfully decreases catalepsy, ptosis, rigidity and akinesia in mice [136].

The body needs vitamin C for various functions. Vitamin C helps the body produce collagen and some neurotransmitters. It acts as an antioxidant; it helps remove reactive oxidative species (ROS) from the body; it helps the body absorb iron. It boosts the immune system. It enhances wound healing [1]. Vitamin C is safe in healthy individuals; the recommended daily dietary dose of vitamin C is approximately 100 mg [121]. High doses of vitamin C for the treatment of various conditions from the common cold to cancer. Vitamin C has been widely used in the treatment and prevention of a large number of chronic disorders like diabetes, common cold, cataracts, glaucoma, macular degeneration, stroke, heart diseases, and cancer [3]. Vitamin C induced a reduction in blood lipid levels in normal and hypercholesterolemic subjects [3], which may protect from atherosclerosis. Vitamin C produces a dose-dependent effect, as antioxidant or anticancer activity; at lower concentrations, it functions as an antioxidant, and at higher pharmacological concentrations, as a pro-oxidant [137]. Vitamin C may be useful for cardiovascular health; as an antioxidant, it helps widen the blood vessels, improve nitric oxide production, and help reduce plaque instability in atherosclerosis; it can protect against heart disease and hypertension [1]. There is a negative correlation between serum vitamin C and total cholesterol [138], and positive correlations between serum vitamin C and HDL [139]; vitamin C may involve in cholesterol metabolism [4]. Supplement therapy of vitamin C is used as adjuvant therapy; it is useful in patients with stress-induced psychiatric disorders [140]. Vitamin C has a

beneficial effect in neurodegenerative diseases as Alzheimer's disease [141]. Vitamin C may help lower the risk of cataracts and slow the progression of age-related macular degeneration, this benefit may be due to vitamin C's antioxidant activity [1]. Vitamin C protects against metal-induced hepatotoxicity [130]. Evidence suggests that vitamin C is a powerful antioxidant in biological systems. In vivo markers of oxidative damage are developed; future studies of the antioxidant effects of vitamin C should target patient groups at high risk of oxidant damage. Moderate intake of vitamin C may produce a hypocholesterolemia effect, and long-term supplementation of vitamin C may be used to keep the lipid profile within normal limits. Vitamin C may have a benefit if it is taken as co-adjuvant therapy by patients with chronic disease.

Ethical issues

Including plagiarism, Informed Consent, data fabrication or falsification and double publication or submission have completely been observed by the author.

Conflict of interest

The author declared no competing interest.

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